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A SOCIO-LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF SELECTED ENUANI PROVERBS

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Abstract

The paper is a sociolinguistic study of selected Enuani proverbs. Enuani refers to one of the dialects of the Igbo language spoken by people of the Aniocha/Oshimili people of Anioma in Delta State of Nigeria. It is used to describe a number of communities that are located within this region including the Ndi Onicha-Ado. It is one of the major dialects of the Igbo of the Southeast but with loaned words from Edo. It is distinguished by accent and mutually intelligible to the group of Anioma people in the state. In all cultures, proverbs form an integral part of people's beliefs, their custom, norms, values and general worldview. Like there Igbo counterpart, the Enuani people relish proverbial expressions as they are, in the words of Chinua Achebe, "the palm oil with which words are eaten". Randomly selected from the author's repertoire of Enuani proverbs as one from the area, 15 proverbs were analyzed using Ethnomethodology. The study found that Enuani proverbs show values of cooperation for peaceful co-existence, cordiality, respect for elders and good conduct. The study is significant because not much scholarly work was done on Enuani dialect, especially its rich proverbial legacy. It is recommended that further studies be carried out on other aspects of the Enuani dialect by interested researchers using different linguistic tools.

KEY WORDS: Ethnomethodology, Enuani, Dialect, Sociolinguistic, Proverbs.

INTRODUCTION

As a Sociolinguistic tool, Ethnomethodology is used to investigate how people use symbol systems that organize their knowledge, values and beliefs. It is a branch of research that studies people's resources of social action, their common sense and interactional competence. The central recommendation of ethnomethodology is how the activities whereby members produce and manage settings of organized daily affairs are identical with their procedures for making those settings accountable. That is, ethnomethodology assumes that the meaning of a social phenomenon is equivalent to the systematic procedures by which participants build and maintain their sense (Harold Garfinkel (1967).

It is not enough to know the correct grammar of a language but one must be able to use it to carry out speech functions within certain contexts. This is what is referred to as sociolinguistic competence. Considering the fact that proverbs are distinctive linguistic resources based on the traditions of their users, this study employs a selection of Enuani proverbs to demonstrate the various processes and techniques language users construct, interact and interpret the world around them in a normal Enuani speech community.

The key concept of ethnomethodology is accountability. Social actions and experiences are accountable; they can be recognized, identified, described, and characterized. By accountability, actions and experiences become regular and fall under normative order. Therefore, ethnomethodology proposes a foundational approach for the constitution of societies and cultures.

A CURSORY LOOK AT PROVERBS

Proverbs are short wise sayings of a people that reflect the sociocultural patterns of the language users within the context of their speech community. They are usually short, memorable, and often highly condensed sayings, embodying some commonplace (especially with bold imagery) fact or experience (Collins Dictionary). Though short in structure, "proverbs are usually loaded proposition expressing simply and concretely, though often metaphorically, truths based on common sense or the practical experience of mankind" (Clarence 1957 cited in Olubumi, 2010).

“Proverbs are a Vehicle for Personal Communication. Similar to other genres of folklore, proverbs perform the function of an impersonal medium for personal communication. Proverbs are used to guide and direct the behaviour or thought of a child or an individual. Once the proverb is quoted and the message is passed across, the responsibility is then shifted from the speaker to the anonymous coiner of the proverb. The addressee then becomes aware of the fact that the proverb did not originate from the speaker but has come from somewhere, sometime ago”(Nwabudike, 2023). Several works have been done on proverbs (Odebode & Eke-Opara 2015; Iyabode, 2016; Olubumi, 2010; Oni & Nwabudike, 2018; Nwabudike, Shima & Amase, 2023).

ABOUT ENUANI AND ITS SPEAKERS

Enuani is one of the dialects of the Igbo language spoken by the people of the Aniocha/Oshimili Anioma people in Delta North, Delta State of Nigeria. Enuani is also used to describe the communities located in a region mentioned above as well as the Ndi Onicha-Ado (Onitsha). It is one of the dialects of the Igbo of the Southeast with loaned words from Edo. The word "Enu" means "High" while "Ani" means "Land". Put together, the word means Highland. Enuani people (Ndi-Enuani) are therefore known as "Highland People" or the "People of Highland".

Enuani is tonal and spoken near Onitsha, Obosi, Atani and Ogbaru in Anambra State. It is standardized and widely accepted. It is often referred to as "Asusu Enuani". It is rarely written but retains Igbo names, words and idiomatic expressions that ordinarily may be understood by other Igbo speakers except minor variations as a result of loan words from the Edoid language. Enuani has cross-pollinated the Aniocha/Oshimili areas characteristically bringing about communication homogeneity with the adoption of words. Other dialects spoken in the Anioma region are Ika, Aboh, Ebu, Ukwani/Ndokwa, Olukunmi etc. They are all derived from Igbo, Yoruba, Edo and Igala.

The Enuani have a homogenous culture; for instance, the Akwa-Ocha (Oto-Ogwu, in some Anioma dialects) fabric is the traditional attire of the Enuani as worn by the entire people of Anioma. It is a white fabric woven with designs sometimes inscribing the "Anioma State" tied around the chest or waist by women fashionably supported with a blouse and also worn around the waist by men or sometimes made

to appear as a very bogus shirt reaching the legs. The Akwa-Ocha) is decorated with beads finely worn around the wrists and hanging loosely around the neck.

As in other cultures, (Enuani) proverbs function like moral codes, conventional wisdom and explicit rules of conduct. These proverbs describe and prescribe the patterns of behaviour. They state the experiences, moral intuitions and guidelines for the people (Nwabudike, 2020).

Like their Igbo counterpart, the Enuani people relish proverbial expressions (Nwabudike, 2023). . Proverbs are central to their beliefs, customs, norms, values and general worldview. This paper aims at bridging to the fore, the rich proverbial heritage of the Enuani people. It is hoped that this study will stimulate further studies on Enuani proverbs using different linguistic theoretical tools like pragmatics, discourse analysis, and others.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a qualitative approach. 15 proverbs reflective of the beliefs and cultural practices of the people were purposively selected from the author's repertoire of Enuani proverbs as a speaker of Enuani and from the stock of proverbs commonly used among the people. The proverbs were then analyzed and interpreted from sociolinguistic standpoint. "When the way language is used is affected by the society in which it is used, especially in areas relating to cultural norms, expectation and context; it becomes the study of sociolinguistics" (Anamayi 2014 cited in Oni & Nwabudike, 2018). This view explains sociolinguistics embraces the aspects of linguistics that evaluate the connection between language and society, and the way we use it in different social contexts. It often shows the humorous relations of human speech and how the dialect of a given language describes the age, sex and social class of the speaker. In essence, it codes the social function of language.

ETHNOMETHODOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF ENUANI PROVERBS

Fairclough (2001, cited in Olubumi, 2010) aver that ethnomethodologists investigate the production and interpretation of everyday action as skilled accomplishments of social factors. Consequently, the interpretation of Enuani proverbs within the contexts of use is a worthy sociolinguistic task for the purpose of showcasing the Enuani speech community as a social world, and communicating the factual properties with which to interpret and interact with that world. For the Enuani speech community, a study of her

proverbs from an ethnomethodological perspective is significant because the proverbs are based on metaphors and other figurative processes that do not occur randomly, but are patterned with other extralinguistic features. Therefore, the values of the proverbs are flexible for various modifications.

1. Gbumwam gbumwam anyamdia

(Literal interpretation: Kill my child, kill my child, my eyes are there. *Meaning:* You naturally protect what belongs to you).

In the traditional Enuani land, everyone condemns vices and commends virtues. In particular, a child in a community is not seen as belonging to just the parents. Therefore, when a child errs any adult close by is expected to correct or discipline that child. However, some persons take disciplining a child to the extreme. And when this is the case, the real parent of the child in question may utter this proverb.

2. Nchekube ka oriri

(Literal interpretation: Hope for tomorrow's provision is greater than the present meal *Meaning:* The future is greater than the present).

Some persons are wont to be contented with what they already have in possession and are less concerned about what is hoped for. This agrees with the English proverb: "A bird in hand is worth two in the bush". But on the contrary, the Enuani proverb *Nchekube ka oriri* cautions against complacency with what one has now to the point of neglecting to plan for the future.

3. Akancha araro

(Literal interpretation: All hands are not equal *Meaning:* People are gifted differently).

This proverb is actually same as the axiom: "All fingers are not equal", although it says 'hands'. It is an indubitable fact in all cultures and climes that people are endowed differently. Some persons have more physical abilities, mental capabilities and financial/materials resources more than others. Because of these differences, there is a need for humility and empathy, not pride, disdain and oppression. This is the message of this proverb.

4. Otutu buike nwata

(Literal interpretation: Morning is a child's strength. *Meaning:* Morning makes the day).

Morning, the beginning of a day, is naturally cool and fresh. Also, morning is the time people wake up after long hours of sleep and rest. And because there is renewed strength and vigor and the brain is renewed, all jobs- physical and mental are better carried out at that time.

5. Nwata wa kwo na azu, amaro na ijediolu

(Literal interpretation: A child on the mother's back does not understand trekking is stressful.

Meaning: Those born with silver spoons in their hands do not feel the pain of labour).

This saying is a word of caution for arrogant despisers of poor and needy individuals in the community. Things may work out easily for some persons, perhaps, because they have inherited landed properties from or have been well trained educationally by their parents or relations. If such persons deride or cast aspersions on the less privileged, this proverb is used for them.

6. Wada mu akaekpe nanlor

(Literal interpretation: Left handedness is not learnt in a dream *Meaning:* Conscious efforts must

be made to do work learn new things).

This adage is close in meaning to the aphorism: "If wishes were horses, even beggars would ride". In traditional Enuani community, hard work is the norm while idleness or laziness is condemned in strong terms. People are encouraged to have realistic plans and work to get what they want rather than relishing wishful thinking and pipe dreams.

7. Wagbasioso wagu mail

(Literal interpretation: At the end of a race the miles are counted.

Meaning: The end justifies the means).

This proverb underscores the importance of goal oriented plans and programmes. What is important is the achievement of a set goal; the means does not matter much. The end justifies the means. This does not, however, mean or encourage that people accomplish their desires 'by hook or by crook' as Enuani people frown at disorderliness. What is encouraged is tenacity of purpose.

8. Wata sina nne amalula amalula

(Literal interpretation: The child that distracts its mother's sleep cannot sleep. *Meaning:* A trouble maker will have trouble himself).

Meekness and gentleness are virtues so cherished by an average Enuani person. Both young and elderly are advised and encouraged to be peaceful. If however, anyone chooses to be troublesome, he or she is reminded by this proverb that even he will share enough in the trouble. The goal is to discourage naughtiness as much as possible.

9. *Aku fesie adari awo*

(Literal interpretation: No matter how long the insect flies, it must fall prey to the frog. *Meaning:* The weak must bow to the strong no matter how long it takes).

This didactic aphorism highlights the prevalence of good over evil or dominance of light over darkness and not just the boasting or show of strength by the powerful against the weak. No matter how long darkness or evil thrives, light or truth will one day surface and overcome it. In a nutshell, people are advised to shun or desist from surreptitious practices.

10. *Wafukaeze ome okpukpu*

(Literal interpretation: When the teeth are often exposed, they look like bones. *Meaning:* Familiarity breeds contempt).

Much as visitation to neighbours, friends or relations and condescending are encouraged, there is a need for restraint in doing so as 'Too much of everything is bad' and familiarity breeds contempt".

11. *Onye onagu nelote na onagu onyeozor*

(Literal interpretation: It is a hungry person that remembers that others are hungry too. *Meaning:* He who feels it knows it; or Experience begets empathy).

It is okay to be sympathetic with people when they are hurt or bereaved but it is better to be empathetic with them. Empathy makes you put yourself in the condition of the hurt or bereaved and it is more impactful than sympathy. However, unless one has had the same experience or similar pain he or she cannot truly empathize with others. This is the message of this proverb.

12. Wejiro akpata etufu ebuogalanye

(Literal interpretation: One does not become rich by being wasteful. Meaning: Wastefulness hinders wealth)

For those who have the tendency to be wasteful or extravagant, this proverb puts them under check or warns them against courting poverty, as wastefulness cannot beget affluence. This axiom encourages prudence and proper management cum maintenances of one's resources.

13. Okei gbasia ocheri ibee

(Literal interpretation: When a man is fully grown, he waits for others to grow too. Meaning: The young shall grow; or age/maturity/ achievement cannot be monopolized).

Whatever is someone's accomplishment, he or she should realize they are neither the first nor the last to do so. The level you are now-age, position, rank, others were there and more will still get there. Success is not the exclusive preserve of one person. This calls for modesty and sobriety.

14. Ogelu wachua na owelenchi

(Literal interpretation: When the time comes, the path of the porcupine shall be searched. Meaning: When we get to the bridge we shall know how to cross it).

There is no need for unnecessary anxiety. The problems of tomorrow should not be borrowed and added to those of today. Issues should be addressed at the appropriate time. Nature also has a way of taking care of knotty issues with time. Life should be lived one day at a time.

15. Wadano nugbo etuonu afia

(Literal interpretation: You can't be on the farm and boast of being an expert weeder. Meaning: The proof of the pudding is in the eating).

Claims and professions should be proved or demonstrated practically and not by mere words. There should be no room for equivocations; prove what you claim to know or have for all to see.

The analysis of Enuani proverbs has no doubt reinforced the role of proverbial expressions as a means of social cohesion through communication. The study shows a word or expression can have both the cognitive and cultural meanings. The cultural meaning of words and expressions reflect the cultural perceptions, values and behaviours such as good character, dignity, respect, patience, diligence, cooperation, love and cordiality in relationships.

Ethnomethodological study shows there is a connection between language, society, context, and culture that justifies the sociolinguistic approach to language study, and emphasizes social appropriateness within a specific context as the basic condition for communicative competence. The study highlights the communicative values of Enuani proverbs as tools of cultural integration, value formation and consequently, cultural identity.

Finally, the study is significant because not much scholarly work was done on Enuani, especially its rich proverbial legacy. The study found that Enuani proverbs show values of cooperation for peaceful co-existence, cordiality, respect for elders and good conduct. It is recommended that further studies be carried out on other aspects of the language by interested researchers using the same sociolinguistic tool.

- Anamayi, R. (2014). A Sociolinguistics Analysis of Classroom Interactional Patterns in Federal College of Forestry Mechanization, Afaka, Kaduna". Zaria: *MA Thesis*, Ahmadu Bello U, Zaria.
- Collins English Dictionary 21st Century Edition. Glasgow: HarperCollins Publishers, 2001.
- Fanany, R. & Fanany I.(2016). Proverbs and Cultural Consonance. *Proverbium*
- Garfi nkel, H. (1967). *Studies in ethnomethodology*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Nwabudike, C., Shima, M. & Amase, G. (2023) "Selected Tiv Proverbs: A Sociolinguistic Analysis" *Bade Journal of Arts (BAJA)*. A Journal Publication of the Faculty of Arts, Federal University Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria.Vol.1, No.1. Pp 42-50.
- Iyabode, O. (2016). Proverbs and Modernity: Taking the Proverbs out of the Mouth of the Elders. *Proverbium 33, The Year Book of International Proverb Scholarship*, The University of Vermont.
- Nwabudike, C. (2020). A Sociolinguistic Analysis of Proverbs in Ola Rotimi's *The Gods Are Not To Blame*. *JOLAN* Volume 23 No 1. *website: www.jolan.org.ng*
- (2023) Achieving National Peace Through Proverbs: A Focus On Enuani Proverbs. A Paper Presented at the 38th Annual Conference of the English Scholars Association of Nigeria (ESAN) held from 11th to 14th September, 2023
- Odebode, I. & Eke-Opara ,C. (2015). Ethnography of Communication" In Ola Rotimi's *The Gods Are Not To Blame: A Pragmatic Study*". *British Journal of English Linguistics*
- Olubumi, I. (2010). An Ethnomethodology of Selected Yoruba Proverbs. *International Journal of Arts and Sciences*, Vol. 3.
- Oni, F. & Nwabudike, C. (2018). Socio-Cognitive Analysis of Selected Proverbs in Ola Rotimi's *Kurunmi*. *Journal of the English Scholars' Association of Nigeria (JESAN)*.Vol. 20, NO 1&2. ISSN: 0029-0009.Pp.284-300.
- The Enuani People of Anioma. Website: www.ibusa.net